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No Justice for Kurds: Turkish Supremacy and Kurdophobia

INTRODUCTION

On July 21, 2021, 60 armed Turks attacked a Kurdish family in the Çarıklar village of Konya, a conservative province in middle Anatolia, and killed Hakim Dal (age 43), while the Turkish gendarmerie stood by (Kamer 2021). The Kurdish family had been displaced from Amed (Diyarbakır) in the southeast in the 1990s and had been raising livestock in Çarıklar village in the Meram District for the past 20 years. This was not the first attack against the family, as other members of the Dal family told the pro-Kurdish media outlet, Mezopotamya Agency, following the murder (Kişin and Yanık 2021). They had been attacked on other occasions; the village chief (*muhtar*) incited villagers against the Kurdish family, and their livestock had been poisoned before. Although the family complained, the authorities stood by until Hakim Dal was murdered in an overt racist attack by his Turkish neighbors. Following the murder, the office of the governor in Konya rushed to make a statement claiming that “the incident is not ethnically motivated, and it happened between two armed groups over a dispute because the livestock [of the Kurdish family] ‘damaged’ the pastures and land [of the local Turks]” (Evrensel Daily 2021). Although the governor’s office claimed that a full investigation was underway, most of the assailants were not arrested, but several members of the Kurdish family were detained.

This was just one of a series of racist attacks against the Kurds across Turkey in July 2021. On the same day, a group of armed Turks (allegedly around 150 people) attacked a Kurdish family in the Altındağ district of Ankara, injuring four members of the Boztaş family—two of them severely. Turkish media presented the incident as a singular criminal case that broke out between neighbors due to a discussion over “animal feces,” whereas a family member told the pro-Kurdish Mezopotamya Agency that “at least 150 people, four of whom were armed, attacked us and severely wounded four of my brothers. They are full of hatred. They will not calm down even if they strangle the Kurds.” Following the racist attacks, the gendarmerie closed entry to the village and did not allow relatives of the Boztaş family to come in, exposing them to further attacks (2021a). Two days before Hakim Dal’s murder, a group of Kurdish seasonal workers came under attack in Sultandağı district of Afyon, in western Turkey. One of the workers was kidnapped by locals, taken to a forest, tortured on camera, and then abandoned, while other workers managed to escape. Victims of the attack made explicit statements to the Kurdish media that they were attacked by the locals in a barbershop because they spoke Kurdish. They were accused of being terrorists and forced to leave the town under threat. Authorities, once again, did nothing but send the Kurdish seasonal workers back to their hometowns in the southeast (Bianet 2021a).

Following the attacks, 15 bar associations in cities with a Kurdish majority issued a statement condemning these racist attacks and warning that these cases should not be treated simply as isolated criminal incidents. They added that the authorities’ increasingly discriminatory language and policies of violence, the negligence of law enforcement, and the lack of effective investigations enabled the attacks (Bianet 2021b). The bar associations, in turn, were targeted by the pro-government Islamist newspaper, *Yeni Şafak*, with the headline, “Kandil’in Baro’nları” (The Barons of Kandil), in reference to the main base of the Kurdistan Workers’ Party’s (PKK) armed forces in Qendîl (Kandil in Turkish) (Şen 2021). The newspaper claimed that these bar

associations support terrorism and fabricate events to spread propaganda. They further alleged that the bar associations and the pro-Kurdish People's Democratic Party (HDP) aim to create chaos by "this manipulation," just as they had when the HDP offices in İzmir and Marmaris were attacked a few months before. The *Yeni Şafak* article failed to mention that these earlier attacks were carried out by ultranationalist Turks with the intention to commit mass murder of 40 party members during a planned meeting later that day (AFP 2021).

The statements by state authorities and their media apparatuses following these racist attacks share features that I characterize as "Turkish supremacy": singularization of systemic racist attacks (*münferit*), manipulation of facts as purely personal (*şahsi*) and "judicial" (*adli*) but not ethnically motivated and racist, media distribution of essentialized state and perpetrators' narratives, dehumanization of Kurdish victims, silencing and discrediting of Kurdish testimonies, and provision of impunity to perpetrators, which encourages further attacks. Turkish supremacy is historically rooted, institutionally reinforced, and socially reproduced in the racist habitus of Turkey. This racist habitus can be best understood via the concept of "Kurdophobia," an intertwined phenomenon of hostility, fear, intolerance, and racism toward Kurdish people, culture, and language among Turkish supremacists and the wider Turkish society. Kurdophobia is integral to Turkish supremacy, which needs to invoke racism against Kurds to sustain its superior position.

HOW KURDS ARE MADE INTO INTERNAL OTHERS

Racism was integral to the Turkish nation-building process, beginning with the late Ottoman period. Selim Deringil observes that the late Ottoman Empire adopted a colonial stance toward the peoples of the empire's periphery, engaging in "borrowed colonialism," "the civilizing mission mentality of the late Ottomans and their project of modernity as reflected in their provincial administration" in Libya. The "white man's burden wearing a fez," Deringil suggests, was a result of the weakening position of the Ottoman Empire against

Western colonialism (2003, 311–13). In his seminal article, “Ottoman Orientalism,” Ussama Makdisi notes, “there has been a reluctance to discuss representations of otherness advanced by non-Western regimes,” and explores “how Ottoman resistance to Western imperialism engendered its own interrelated forms of Orientalist representation and domination that existed simultaneously at the center and the periphery” (2002, 795). He suggests, “Ottoman Orientalism was not inadvertent but a pervasive and defining facet of Ottoman modernity” at a time when the defining political discourse of the empire shifted from religion versus heresy to modernization versus backwardness (769–80).

Nationalism was central to this new construct, first in the form of Ottoman nationalism and later Turkish nationalism, through a process of Turkification following the partition of Arab states from the empire. The Armenian Genocide in 1915 and other subsequent massacres of non-Muslim minorities (Greeks, Assyrians) in the early twentieth century laid the foundation for the Turkification of the newly established republic. Barış Ünlü formulates this transition around the two interconnected “contracts” of Muslimness and Turkishness by which selective privileges are granted. The earlier “Muslimness contract” had two essential components: to be a Muslim and thereby to benefit from privileges; and to be complicit in and/or silent about what happened to Armenians and other non-Muslim constituents of the late Ottoman Empire. By 1925, Ünlü suggests, the Muslimness contract was narrowed down to the “Turkishness contract,” as now one also had to be Turkish, or to perform and declare loyalty to Turkishness, in order to benefit from the privileges. The other major modification to the contract was that compliance and silence extended to matters relating to the Kurds and the state’s violent practices towards them (Ünlü 2016, 399–400):

As per the Turkishness Contract, every Turk or Turkified individual would potentially benefit even though she or he is not an active signatory, meaning that not every

individual had to participate in the state's genocidal and oppressive policies toward Armenians and Kurds. The crucial point was not to resist and breach the contract. The contract afforded its Turkified members a certain expectation of social mobility across the socioeconomic spectrum. In other words, if the contract was respected, the individual and his or her family members would potentially be able to climb the ladder in politics, business, bureaucracy, academy, art, etc. But those who were in breach of the contract were to be severely punished in the form of killing, torture, imprisonment, unemployment, stigmatization and/or ostracism. (400)

By the time the Turkish Republic was established in 1923, the Kurds were the only remaining internal Muslim-majority others that could pose a threat within the new borders of the Turkish ethno-national state. Hence, the Kurdish national rebellions of Sheikh Said in 1925, the Ararat Uprising of 1927–1930, the Dersim Rebellion in 1938, and other uprisings across Turkey's Kurdistan were all violently suppressed (Yadırgı 2017, 165–73). Major repressive policies, such as the establishment of general inspectorates (Umumi Müfettişlik) in 1928, were enacted at this time for the remaking of Kurdish society (Aslan 2011, 80). The 1934 Settlement Law extended this effort by dividing the Kurdish region into three zones to (1) increase the Turkish population in Kurdish majority areas (zone one), (2) assimilate Kurds by exiling them to Turkish majority areas (zone two), and (3) depopulate certain areas and prohibit resettlement of any sort (zone three) (Yadırgı 2017, 182). Even though this law was not fully implemented and the general inspectorates were terminated in 1952, the Kurdish region remained under de facto martial law and was ruled by states of emergency law.

From the 1920s to the 1990s, the state policy was to deny the existence of Kurds (who were claimed to be “mountain Turks”), prohibit the usage of Kurdish language, and suppress any cultural expression

of Kurdishness in public space. What was at stake was Kurdish nationhood (Bayrak 2014), but the official Turkish state discourse framed the Kurdish national struggle as a question of regional underdevelopment or a tribal reaction to the project of modernization (Yeğen 1999). Through this construct, the Turkish state positioned itself as “the savior of the Kurds” from their backward feudal, tribal, and religious oppressors, while also denying Kurdish existence altogether.

After the Kurdistan Workers’ Party (PKK) began its armed struggle against the Turkish state in 1984, the Kurdish region was once again governed through a state of emergency (OHAL) between 1987 and 2002. The Turkish white man had taken off his fez but his “civilizing” mission against the Kurds raged on. During the “dirty war” of the 1990s, the entire Kurdish region became a war zone: over 3 million Kurds were forcibly displaced, their villages and property were burned, every aspect of their lives was securitized, and all manifestations of their language and culture were criminalized. The ongoing conflict between the state and the armed Kurdish resistance cost over 60,000 lives, the majority of them Kurdish civilians. During this period, a few million Kurds moved to the western and coastal cities of Turkey for security and financial reasons, where they encountered urban poverty, discrimination, stigmatization, and every form of racism. After a number of ceasefires by the PKK in the early 2000s and a short period of peace negotiations between the state and the mainstream Kurdish political movement in the 2010s, the political conflict reignited in 2015 and resulted in the displacement of another half a million Kurdish civilians (most of whom had already been displaced from their villages in the 1990s), this time from Kurdish urban centers. Over a hundred Kurdish areas have been declared “special security regions” or “temporary military security regions,” which prohibits entry to and suspends rule of law in these areas. Moreover, several Kurdish districts remained under continuous curfews for months, and Kurdish civilians in these designated areas were victims of severe human rights violations and state crimes.

Following the failed military putsch in July 2016, the Islamist Justice and Development Party (AKP) declared a nationwide state of emergency and ruled the country through martial law until 2018. Although the Kurds had nothing to do with the military putsch, they bore the brunt of the deterioration of political conditions. Leaders and thousands of pro-Kurdish People's Democratic Party (HDP) members, Kurdish activists, teachers and students, and members of pro-Kurdish trade unions and civil society organizations were imprisoned and/or dismissed from their positions, while their organizations were shut down via emergency decrees. Although the nationwide state of emergency ended in 2018, the Kurdish region remained under a de facto state of emergency, where every aspect of Kurdish life is securitized and elected Kurdish mayors are consistently dismissed from their positions through fabricated terrorism charges. State-appointed trustees to Kurdish municipalities run Kurdish cities as their personal fiefdoms, planting surveillance cameras and watchmen in every corner, restricting entry and exit via an unwarranted high number of security checkpoints.

It is against this backdrop that Kurdish ethnic identity has become racialized, with a host of negative attributions regarding their physical appearance, accent, morality, criminality, and civilization level (Ergin 2014, 329–32). This Kurdophobic language portrays the Kurds “as culturally backward, intrinsically incapable of adapting to ‘modern city life,’ naturally criminal, violent and separatist people” while casting “the increasing number of Kurds in Western Turkish cities as the ‘Kurdish invasion’” (Bora 2006, 78, cited in Saraçoğlu 2009, 641). Cenk Saraçoğlu claims that anti-Kurdish sentiments in Turkish spaces can be formulated as “exclusive recognition,” which exhibits four common features. First, this anti-Kurdish discourse recognizes the Kurds as a separate group, which is at odds with the state's assimilationist discourse. Second, this discourse excludes the Kurds via negative attributions and stereotyping. Third, these perceptions are justified based on “superficial contacts with and observations of Kurdish migrants in the everyday life of Turkish cities.” Finally, these

pejorative labels are used exclusively against the Kurds, but not other minorities (Saraçoğlu 2009, 642). It should be noted that this “exclusive recognition” is a result of the failure of the assimilationist policies and in no way implies progress in the Kurdish struggle for recognition and equal rights. Rather, it indicates how pervasive racism has become in Turkish everyday life.

TURKISH SUPREMACY AND KURDOPHOBIA

Turkish supremacy is historically rooted, institutionally reinforced, and socially reproduced. It relies on the assumed “whiteness” of the Turks in a racialized metaphor of privilege and subordination. In the political lexicon of Turkey, whiteness and blackness are utilized by politicians across the secularist and Islamist spectrum to criticize the elitist position of the rival political group in order to position themselves as being for the ordinary people, who are metaphorically “Black.” The binary of “white vs. black Turks” was once utilized by the Islamists against the secularists, yet has more recently been reversed by the Islamist AKP government’s consolidation of power, as now the Islamists are the new “whites” (Güner 2021).

This relational dichotomy excludes the Kurds. Following the same racialized metaphorical lexicon, I suggest that Turkish supremacy ensures its own “whiteness” while relegating Kurds, so long as they retain their Kurdish identity, to “blackness.” In this construct, Kurds are prevented from having access to the social mobility allowed to Turks. I draw my claim from the consistency of the superior position afforded to Turks, whether in the case of the progressive modernity of early republican secularist Turks or in the case of the more recent neo-Ottomanist nationalism of Islamist Turks. In each case, the Turkish white man’s burden persists in its effort to assimilate Kurds into its own political construct (secularist modernity, Kemalism, socialism, Islamism, etc.), while preserving the superior position of the Turks.

For the first half of the twentieth century, the Kurds were construed as backward internal others to be assimilated into modern

Turkishness. Kemalists attempted to create a monolithic Turkish nation that disregarded the country's ethnic diversity. Once the Islamist nationalist parties and coalitions assumed power in the 1980s, and more recently since the 2000s, the construct has shifted to an Islamic fraternity and neo-Ottomanism that aims to assimilate Kurds into an Islamist ideology in which Turkish supremacy and the subordinate position of the Kurds are to be sustained. In both instances, the Kurds are forcibly "invited" to subordinate to a superior position. In the neo-Ottomanist Islamist claim of "religious fraternity," for example, Turks are assigned as the leaders of the Islamic *ummah* (community) as an extension of the Ottoman past (Türkmen 2021). In this construct, the Kurds' Kurdishness is forgiven as long as they are compliant Muslim little brothers and sisters to the Turks. A Turk can be a *Turkish* Muslim (and even lead the *ummah* retaining their name and history), whereas a Kurd would have to shed their Kurdishness. The same applies to Turkish internationalists and the majority of socialists, as they tend to view Kurdish claims for liberation as a conspiracy of international powers against the spirit of anti-imperialism and class struggle. Like utopian Islamists who postpone solving urgent problems to an imaginary future Islamic administration, socialists of Turkey postpone urgent Kurdish problems to an imaginary future socialist revolution. Turkish liberals and neo-Kemalists (across the political spectrum) present the Kurdish question as a question of underdevelopment, democratic progress, and liberal rights. In all instances, Kurds are assigned to the inferior position, as those who need to be saved from their oppressors, protected from international powers and their conspiracies (*dış güçler*) or even from themselves. Meanwhile, attacks against the human dignity of Kurds are rarely discussed within the parameters of Turkish supremacy and its need for an inferior other.

Around the time the Kurdish families and seasonal workers were exposed to racist attacks, the coastal areas of southern and western Turkey were suffering from devastating forest fires. Here again, the Justice and Development Party (AKP) authorities, despite their own evident inadequate emergency response, pinned the blame on

the Kurds by declaring that the fires were set by the PKK. This propaganda found wide support across the country and on social media, fueling racist attacks against Kurds in areas surrounding the fires. Turkish villagers started setting up security checkpoints as self-appointed militias, checking the IDs of civilians escaping the fires and attacking Kurds who were there as firefighters, seasonal workers, or vacationers. The victims and damage caused by the coastal forest fires found a wide network of solidarity and sympathy across the country and received a lot of media attention. The similarly devastating forest fires that erupted in the Kurdish regions of Dersim and Şırnak have not elicited the same outrage from the Turkish general public. Turkish supremacy does not only affect people but extends into habitats and their political ecologies.

On July 30, 2021, only nine days after the murder of Hakim Dal, in the same city of Konya, a Kurdish family of seven was brutally murdered and their house set on fire. The Dedeoğulları family, similar to the Dal family, had been displaced from the eastern Kurdish city of Kars in the 1990s and had been raising livestock in the Hasanköy village of Konya's Meram district for the past 24 years. They had been attacked by their neighbors before: on May 12, 2021, a group of 60 people broke into their house, chanting "we are nationalists (ülküçü, "Gray Wolves"),¹ and we will not allow the Kurds to live here," and severely wounded seven people. The racist assailants, well aware of the impunity provided by state authorities in similar situations, even said to "call the police and let them come to help you" during the attack. They were right. When the police arrived at the scene, they pinned the blame on the Kurdish family. Only 10 of the 60 assailants were detained, of which only six were arrested. Two months later, on July 9, four others were released at the first court hearing, leaving only two under arrest. Ten of the assailants were even provided a civil protection order by the court. In the ruling about their release, the court stated that this decision was on the grounds of "conscientious opinion" (*vicdani kanaat gerekçesiyle tahliyelerine*).

The suspects have been wounded and are victims themselves [in the attack they perpetrated]. Their criminal records are old [meaning the court does not believe that they will commit further crimes]. They are farmers and approaching summer days are harvest time for them [let the poor farmers harvest]. There is a possibility that the accusations may be dropped in favor of the suspects [in the next hearing, for sure!]. They have served enough time under arrest, and the objective of this arrest has been achieved. The same objective can also be achieved via a judicial control. For all these reasons and due to the principles of justice, fairness, and moderation, and on the grounds of our conscientious opinion, the suspects Yahya Çalık and Veli Keleş have been released via judicial control.²

It was by this “conscientious opinion” of the Turkish justice system that the Dedeoğulları family was murdered three weeks later. In the days leading up to the murder, Barış Dedeoğulları told Mezopotamya Agency:

The physical attacks have now turned into verbal attacks. Those who received a civil protection order from the court come to the front of our house every day, swearing sexist insults, and leaving. We have now given up hope on security and the justice system. I know better now that there is no justice for Kurds. We do not know what to do. My sister’s arm is broken, she will not be able to use her hand for the rest of her life. Where is justice? There is justice for everyone, but no justice for Kurds. (2021b)

Barış would pay a heavy price for the clarity of his observations a few days later, when he was murdered along with six other family members. The family’s lawyer, Abdurrahman Karabulut, revealed that the murder was collectively planned via a WhatsApp group created in

May 2021 (Gazete Duvar 2021). The murderer, Mehmet Altun, was the brother-in-law of Lütfi Keleş, one of the two remaining arrestees from the May attack. He gained entry into the house by introducing himself as a municipality official and, once inside, tried to blackmail the family into withdrawing their complaints against his brother-in-law and force them to sign a document. When his offer was rejected, he pulled out a gun from a plastic bag and killed all seven family members and set the house on fire in order to destroy the security camera footage. Immediately after the murders, the infamous interior minister, Süleyman Soylu,³ made a statement that “the incident has nothing to do with the Kurdish-Turkish issue. This is a result of an animosity that has been going on for 11 years. Any evaluation that presents this incident as ethnically motivated is abuse and provocation that targets the unity of this country” (Gazete Vatan 2021). Similar statements were made by other state authorities, insisting that the murders were separate rather than systemic incidents and that any claim otherwise was a provocation against the unity of the country. The pro-government *Hürriyet Daily News* went as far as to claim that the ongoing animosity had started over a stolen cat 11 years ago (Kızılkoyun 2021).

Just like the murder of Hakim Dal in Konya and the injuries of four members of the Boztaş family in Ankara, the Dedeoğulları family’s murder was reduced to a purely personal matter. Implications that the reasons of these attacks lie in “animal feces,” stolen cats, and livestock grazing in the wrong pastures are not neutral—they are revealing of a project of dehumanizing Kurds. Mesut Yeğen demonstrates that in the first half of the twentieth century, Turkish nationalism perceived the Kurdish question in terms of the fatal rivalry between the backward, premodern, and tribal past of the Kurds and the prosperous present of the Turks (Yeğen 1999). This reductionist and dehumanizing approach increases instrumental violence (Rai, Valdesolo, and Graham 2017) and fosters negative attitudes, especially toward immigrants and outsiders (Utych 2018). Statements from the authorities also aim to suppress possible discontent and threaten those who dare to speak the truth. The police prevented journalists

who were following the murder of the Dedeoğulları family in Konya from speaking to the victims' relatives, saying "there are instructions not to allow the journalists" (Mezopotamya Ajansı 2021c). Öznur Değer, a reporter for the pro-Kurdish women's news agency, Jinnews (Bianet 2021c), and Özgür Boğatekin, a news editor of a local media outlet in Gerger district of Adıyaman, were charged with "inciting public to hatred and hostility" as per Article 216 of the Turkish Penal Code (TCK) because of their journalistic work covering the murders and their social media posts criticizing the racist attacks against the Kurds (Adal 2021).

Article 216 of the TCK is in place for this exact purpose: to ensure that Turkish supremacy is institutionally reinforced. Critical voices are controlled and punished to bolster the state's justification. It is almost always a Kurd or a member of a non-Turkish/non-Sunni minority who is charged with "inciting the public to hatred and hostility"—a public that does not include the Kurds. Indeed, there are other articles of the TCK that protect Turkish supremacy. Article 301, for example, punishes insulting Turkishness, the Turkish nation, or Turkish state institutions with up to two years of prison. Insulting the Kurds or other minorities is considered "freedom of expression" by the Turkish supremacist justice system. This is how Turkish supremacy is produced and protected via institutions and maintained through impunity provided for such racist attacks.

Finally, Turkish supremacy is also socially reproduced. Turkey's racist habitus, formed over the century since its founding, is manufactured by the state and its institutions to be distributed via education and media apparatuses. The veneration of Turkishness begins at an early age with the recitation of the pledge at school (which ends with "how happy one is who says I am a Turk"), while all other ethnic and religious identities go unmentioned. The fiction of Turkish superiority also entails that Turkey is surrounded by internal and external enemies, and minority labels such as Kurd, Armenian, or Jew are leveraged for humiliation and insult. As Bariş Ünlü observes, a Turk does not necessarily have to sign the Turkishness contract to

be able to benefit from the privileges afforded to them. A Turk need not fear as long as they maintain silence and complicity in public (Ünlü 2016, 400), whereas a Kurd is expected to perform their loyalty to Turkishness at every turn in order to avoid stigmatization as a terrorist, separatist, or backward feudal/tribal/bigot. These performances lead many Kurds to seek refuge in universalist ideologies such as socialism, Islamism, and humanism. “We are all members of the same ummah and we are brothers and sisters,” “we are all human,” “we are all part of the same nation and citizens of the same country” are phrases one might hear spoken by Kurds living and working in Turkish spaces. Voluntary assimilation and internalized Kurdophobia become viable survival mechanisms, as they allow for upward mobility. After all, “how happy is the one who says I am a Turk” is the motto of the Turkish Republic since its founding father, Atatürk, used the phrase on the tenth anniversary of the foundation of the republic on October 29, 1933. The motto is written on Kurdish valleys as a reminder that happiness is not guaranteed unless you submit to Turkishness. But is happiness even guaranteed if you declare your assumed Turkishness? What other performances are expected from Kurds in this regard? What are some typical Kurdophobic stereotypes and behaviors they encounter on a daily basis? What kind of strategies do they develop to avoid stigmas and cross invisible boundaries of Turkish supremacy?

UNWRITTEN CODES: EVERYDAY KURDOPHOBIA

Kurdophobia dates back to the fall of the Ottoman Empire when the Kurds were the only remaining ethnic majority that was not successful in the struggle for liberation, which sparked a strong “fear of separation” among the founders of the Turkish state. The assimilationist strategies employed to fight this fear were not fully successful, except in creating fear, hostility, and hatred within Turkish society toward the Kurds, whose subjectivities, in turn, were shaped by this new racist habitus. The racialization of Kurdish ethnic identity hastened with the Kurdish migration to western Turkish cities for financial or

security reasons. Before this, the Kurds were mainly a distant image in the minds of Turks, barbaric and uncivilized people who had to be tamed and civilized. After the en masse migration of the 1990s amid the intensifying conflict between the state and the PKK, Kurds became “baby killers,” “separatists and terrorists,” “unreliable and untrustworthy,” “dirty and immoral” people. It became an urgent matter to protect Turkish people from these “uncivilized” people, who were now invading Turkish spaces. This rhetoric of invasion reveals the unwritten Turkish supremacist codes that rule over Kurdish lives.

These unwritten codes become manifest in the division of “good” and “bad” Kurds. The exact definition and boundaries of this division are elusive, shifting according to the oppressor’s interests at any given moment. A useful analogy can be found in Malcolm X’s distinction between “the house Negro” and “the field Negro.” The “house Negro” is an enslaved person who is living in or close to the master’s house and has a symbiotic relation with him, whereas the “field Negro” could only thrive if the suppression and exploitation of the master ends.⁴ Similarly, the “good Kurds” are the ones “who do not look like the Kurds” and are loyal to their oppressor’s interests. They work hard to free themselves of any association with Kurdishness (dress, accent, culture, hometown, politics, etc.), and are relatively integrated into the system of Turkish supremacy. They have internalized racism and are hostile toward “bad Kurds,” who remind them of what they once were. The “good Kurds” are at the forefront of every political ideology because they need to prove themselves as devotees of the oppressor’s cause. They sacrifice themselves for the “Islamic ummah,” “socialist revolution,” or “the indivisible unity of the homeland.” Still, they are met with suspicion and are reminded of where they come from at times of crisis.⁵

The “bad Kurd,” on the other hand, is anyone who does not willingly abide by the Turkishness contract. Among the “bad Kurds” are those willing but unable to become “good Kurds” because they are “too dark skinned,” “too hairy,” “too accented” or lack the necessary means to assimilate because of the structural inequalities

shaping their conditions. Nonetheless, the “bad Kurds” are not necessarily political Kurds nor must hold a strong notion of Kurdish ethnic identity but are shaped by their Kurdish habitus and easily detectable in Turkish spaces. The “bad Kurds” are generally underprivileged Kurds, although it does not mean that privilege is a guaranteed way out from stigmatization and Kurdophobia. However, underprivileged Kurds are more vulnerable to stigmatization and easily detectable by the Turks, state authorities, and security forces.

In a recent conversation with a group of Kurdish men in their late thirties, I asked if they had encountered any bad treatment or were reminded of their Kurdishness in the last month. “I am never allowed to forget my Kurdishness,” one of them replied. Another told us how he was stopped and searched at a security checkpoint when he was driving toward western Turkey recently: “They saw that my car’s plate number is from Mardin and singled me out among many others driving by. You know how I look [referring to his dark skin and bushy beard], so they invited me inside a tent for a detailed search. They even called for a search dog for my car. The police officer who came with the dog asked me what I do, so I told him that I am a teacher. Surprised, he asked why I hadn’t said so earlier and let me go.” “But you are not a teacher,” I replied. “I know,” he said, “but if you are a Kurd, you should know how to navigate.” I asked him how he felt about the police. “You ask questions as if you are not a Kurd yourself. We never go to the police, you know that.” “I know, I know. Just wanted to ask for the record,” I replied. “I still feel uneasy whenever I enter a governmental building or see a police officer. I use my best Turkish and behave very respectfully to avoid trouble,” he continued. “Did you realize that there are so many checkpoints, and they stop you on each of them when you leave the Kurdish region, but they do not do that when you come in? As if we live in another country,” a third one pointed out. The fourth in the group responded, “How tough we have become because of the collective sufferings we endured. This is our advantage, we can find our way even in the hardest conditions, but a Turk cannot. I laugh out loud at the little problems

that they cannot endure.” The last one in the group said that he was asked to define what terrorism is when he recently interviewed for a government position. “They eliminated me because they did not like my answer. They are afraid of us,” he said.

In this focus group interview, everyone had a recent experience with discrimination. The level of perceived injustice was obvious from their responses, and they had a strong sense of collective suffering and identity. They were all aware of racialization and profiling of the Kurds, although they did not necessarily frame it as such. Instances of racialization based on physical appearance, accent, birthplace when asked for an ID card by security forces—or when asked by ordinary Turks—were among the examples they gave. As the author of this article and a Kurd, I was not unfamiliar with such incidents. I also had countless stop-and-frisk encounters and experienced discrimination all my life in Turkish spaces. I have watched the facial expressions of Turks change when I told them where I was from. “It is ok, they [Kurds] are also human” is a response I, and likely millions of Kurds, am used to hearing. I have been reminded of my Kurdishness at every turn, been expected to perform loyalty to the state and speak on behalf of all Kurds. When I stated an opinion that went against the norms of Turkish supremacy, I would be met with an infantilizing response telling me what was right to think or say. Even among the majority of so-called progressive and critical Turks, I observed and experienced that a Kurd was the last one to be listened to, if ever.

These experiences of hostility toward Kurds are not examples of “a few bad apples” in state institutions or among the Turkish public but indicators of how deeply ingrained Kurdophobia is in the everyday life of Turkey. Much of these Kurdophobic behaviors go unacknowledged and unchallenged because Turkish supremacy is well established in Turkey’s racist habitus and because the state ensures impunity to Turks for such transgressions. As I write this article, on the evening of September 3, 2021, a seven-year-old Kurdish boy, Mihraç Miroğlu, was hit and killed by an armored police vehicle in the İdil district of Şırnak. The driver of the vehicle was never put in

custody. He was set free after giving his testimony that he was not driving fast—no further investigation necessary (Rudaw 2021). According to the Human Rights Association (İnsan Hakları Derneği, İHD), Mihraç was the fortieth Kurdish civilian to die in such “accidents” since 2008 in the Kurdish region, whereas only two civilians died under similar conditions in western Turkey during the same time period (İHD 2019). At least 17 of these “casualties” were children and six of them were women, and none of the perpetrators faced deterrent sentences by the Turkish courts. Nihat Eren, the head of Diyarbakır Bar Association, claims that such deaths are a result of the policies of impunity and ineffective investigation stemming from the belief that such indictments could harm the image of the police, who are in the region to maintain security.⁶ Again, what is at stake is Turkish supremacy and its well-protected domains against Kurdish civilians. Justice becomes a secondary concern, if any, and every aspect of Kurdish lives becomes securitized. Barış Dedeoğulları’s statement before his murder along with his family members in Konya, hence, was not only a personal observation but a collective cry of the Kurdish people, who are well aware that “there is no justice for Kurds” in Turkey.

CONCLUSION

This was only a month in the life of Kurds in Turkey. As the internal others of Turkish supremacy, Kurds have never been at peace under the Turkish ethno-national state and its assimilationist and oppressive policies. The late Ottoman Empire’s project of “borrowed colonialism” against its internal others in the periphery might have failed, yet its orientaling gaze and its “civilizing mission” survived into the Turkish Republic and continued to evolve. Turkish supremacy, rooted in the notion of the indivisibility of the nation, viewed the Kurdish struggle for unity and liberation as a separatist threat and sought to discredit and suppress Kurdish leaders and insurgents as “bandits” or “terrorists,” while putting an entire population under century-long policies of denial, assimilation, and Kurdophobia.

Presenting the Kurdish struggle for liberation, recognition, and equal rights as backward and reactionary against the progressive modernity of the Turkish nation-state required massive material, institutional, and discursive mobilization. Kurdophobia, integral to the reproduction of this supremacist mentality, became widespread with the mass migration of Kurds to western Turkish cities during the “dirty war” of the 1990s. Previously, Kurds had been a matter of concern mainly for the state and its apparatuses, but now they occupied a different role across Turkish cities and towns as new residents, farmers, businesspeople, and seasonal and construction workers. These encounters challenged normative Turkish assumptions about Kurds and tested Turkish supremacy, as the Kurdish struggle for equal rights and recognition could no longer be dismissed as an isolated problem of the distant east.

Although the 2010s brought nominal attempts at reconciliation, with peace negotiations between the state and the mainstream Kurdish political movement, the Kurdish emancipation in northern and eastern Syria threatened Turkish indivisibility, and Kurdophobic sentiments and attacks skyrocketed. By 2015, the peace negotiations had failed, and a full-fledged conflict had displaced half a million Kurds and caused two thousand deaths. Since the failed coup attempt of 2016, countless Kurds have been imprisoned, purged from their jobs, or gone into exile. Furthermore, the whole Kurdish region has been under close surveillance: access to the Kurdish region is closely monitored; public gatherings, celebrations, protests, and rallies are banned by state authorities; members and activists of the mainstream Kurdish political movement are continually threatened, arrested, and prevented from fulfilling their political duties; and the entire Kurdish population, inside and outside Turkish borders, is dehumanized. The coalition between the Islamist AKP and ultranationalist MHP has found a fertile ground for electoral success by inciting nationalist sentiments and reinforcing Turkish supremacy against the Kurds. It is in this political climate that Kurds are murdered and discriminated

against on a daily basis while the true nature of this systemic Kurdophobia is painted over as “Islamic fraternity” or “anti-imperialist struggle” by the political components of Turkish supremacy.

More recently, this discriminatory repertoire toward internal others has also provided a blueprint for anti-refugee sentiment and xenophobia across the country. While Kurds were being targeted by racist attacks in the summer of 2021, Syrian and Afghan refugees in Turkey were also targeted. In the Altındağ district of Ankara, a whole Syrian neighborhood was raided by thousands of Turkish civilians while the security forces stood by. Syrian stores and houses were burned down or destroyed by the “angry crowds” who accused Syrians of escaping the war rather than fighting for their country. It seems that Turkish supremacy has found its new internal others in the Syrian and Afghan refugees, as they are described with pejorative terms, humiliated because of escaping the war, and dehumanized as uncivilized and barbaric people invading Turkish cities and stealing Turkish jobs. Turkish supremacists are using the same vocabulary against the Syrian and Afghan refugees that they have been using against the Kurds for decades, although the newly arriving Syrians and Afghans retain some linguistic and cultural rights not afforded to Kurds. The extent of this xenophobia and its intersections with the well-established system of Kurdophobia in Turkey need further investigation beyond the capacity of this paper and will be dealt with in another publication.

NOTES

1. Ülkücüs are known as Gray Wolves and are a part of the racist far-right political party, the Nationalist Movement Party (MHP), a coalition partner of the ruling AKP.
2. <http://mezopotamyaaajansi35.com/tum-haberler/content/view/141038>, accessed Aug. 25, 2021. “Şüphelilerin yarananmış olmaları nedeniyle mağduriyetleri, adli sicil kayıtlarının eski tarihli olduğu, çiftçilik işi ile iştikâl etme nedeniyle gelen günlerin yaz günü hasat zamanı olması, üzerlerine atılan suçun vasıf ve mahiyetinin şüpheliler

lehine deęişme ihtimali bulunduęu, řüphelilerin tutuklulukta geirdięi süre, tutuklama tedbiri ile saęlanmak istenen maksadın hasıl olduęu, aynı maksadın bu aşamada adli kontrol tedbiri ile de saęlanabileceęi, hak, nesafet, ölçölülük ilkeleri gereęince ve vicdanı kanaat gerekesiyle, sanıklardan Yahya alık ve Veli Keleş hakkında adli kontrol tedbiri konularak tahliyesine kararı verildi.”

3. Soyly’s name was recently revealed as a part of international narco-trafficking from Venezuela and his ties with the mafia networks in Turkey was confirmed by one of his former co-criminals, Sedat Peker.
4. <https://ccnmtl.columbia.edu/projects/mmt/mxp/speeches/mxa17.html>, accessed on 02 September 2021
5. The lifetime Islamist Bülent Arın, who served as the head of the parliament and in other high positions in the AKP government, for example, was reminded of his Kurdishness by the leader of the Nationalist Movement Party (MHP), Devlet Baheli, when he made a statement for the release of the imprisoned leader of the People’s Democratic Party (HDP), Selahattin Demirtaş, and businessman Osman Kavala. “Dear Arın, what is your purpose, what are you trying to achieve by sympathizing with terrorists? Are you returning to your roots? Are you sympathizing with your breed? Demanding the release of these two people means praising the criminals. It means that you are complicit in these crimes, and you are a traitor.” Accessed Sept. 2, 2021.
6. <https://www.dw.com/tr/13-yılda-40-kıřiyi-öldüren-zırhlı-aralar-gerekten-gerekli-mi/a-59107178>, accessed Sept. 7, 2021.

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